

C O R T E X ²

D4.4 – Analysis of psychosocial factors to optimize CORTEX²

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AR	Augmented Reality
HeMDs	Helmet-Mounted Displays
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IoT	Internet of Things
MR	Mixed Reality
SD	Standard Deviation
SUS	System Usability Scale
VAC	Vergence-Accommodation Conflict
VCAA	Video Compression and Alternative Appearance
VE	Virtual Environments
VR	Virtual Reality
XR	Extended Reality

Spearman correlation: Used to discover the strength of a link between two sets of data.

Standard deviation: Measure used to quantify the variation or dispersion of a set of numerical data.

The CORTEX² project

The COVID-19 pandemic pushed individuals and companies worldwide to work primarily from home or change their work model to stay in business. Today, all the signs show that remote work is here to stay. But not all organizations are ready to adapt to this new reality, where team collaboration is vital.

Existing services and applications aimed at facilitating remote team collaboration — from video conferencing systems to project management platforms — are not yet ready to efficiently and effectively support all types of activities. And extended reality (XR)-based tools, which can enhance remote collaboration and communication, present significant challenges for most businesses.

The mission of CORTEX² is to democratize access to the remote collaboration offered by next-generation XR experiences across a wide range of industries and SMEs.

To this aim, CORTEX² will provide the following:

- Full support for **augmented reality (AR) experiences** as an extension of video conferencing systems when using heterogeneous service end devices through a novel Mediation Gateway platform.
- Resource-efficient **teleconferencing tools** through innovative transmission methods and automatic summarization of shared long documents.
- Easy-to-use and powerful **XR experiences** with instant 3D reconstruction of environments and objects, and simplified use of natural gestures in collaborative meetings.
- Fusion of vision and audio for **multichannel semantic interpretation** and enhanced tools such as **virtual conversational agents** and **automatic meeting summarization**.
- Full **integration of Internet of Things (IoT) devices into XR experiences** to optimize interaction with running systems and processes.
- **Optimal extension possibilities and broad adoption** by delivering the core system with **open APIs** and launching **open calls** to enable further technical extensions, more comprehensive use cases, and deeper evaluation and assessment.

Overall, **we will invest a total of 4 million Euros in two open calls**, which will be aimed at:

1. recruiting tech start-ups/SMEs to co-develop CORTEX².
2. engaging new use cases from different domains to demonstrate CORTEX² replication through specific integration paths.
3. assessing and validating the social impact associated with XR technology adoption in internal and external use cases.

The CORTEX² consortium is formed by 10 organizations in 7 countries, which will work together for 36 months.

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1. Introduction

This document includes an analysis of the social and psychological factors to be taken into account during the development of CORTEX². From this analysis, a set of specifications has been derived, which should be understood as development requirements that may evolve throughout the platform's development, based on the results of the tests that will be conducted after the completion of this document.

This document also includes the specifications to create the advisory board of users, which will provide feedback in different stages of the development of CORTEX².

1.1. Methodology

To address the extraction of specifications for the platform, a thorough analysis of social and psychological factors to be considered was initially conducted. This analysis has been described in Section 2 of this document. Based on this data, points that could potentially impact the platform were selected, leading to a set of specifications to be taken into account.

From the project's use cases described in D5.1 – CORTEX² Requirements and Deployment Architecture version 1, and considering the factors that may influence users' opinions, demographic and social data of interest were extracted for inclusion criteria in the studies and the advisory board of users. This data has been extensively described in Section 3.

After extracting specifications from the theoretical study of social and psychological factors, a preliminary study with users was conducted. Since the user's image displayed to others when using such technologies involves a significant portion of these factors, this initial study focused on that aspect. The results and their analysis are described in Section 4.

For a better overview of the requirements obtained in this document, a summary of the same has been provided in Section 5.

1.2. Future work

This task is completed, but the results will be used as a starting point for Task T4.5: Validation of Psychological and Social Factors in Pilots (M13-M36). In this task, the results of the evaluation of the initial specifications will be presented during an iterative process throughout the project. This process will involve various studies based on the phase and type of users involved in each evaluation. It should be noted that during the subsequent studies, these initial specifications may evolve as more comprehensive studies are conducted.

2. Social and psychological factors

Social, psychological, and biological factors are those whose particular qualities determine a specific lifestyle for each individual (Echeburúa et al., 2014). On the one hand, social factors refer to all the external influences we receive from our environment. That is, those aspects that come from close circles and impact what we think and feel: family, friends, coworkers, or the local community. On the other hand, psychological factors are subjective pieces of information that people interpret and take into consideration when making a decision.

Both types of factors play a significant role in a user's decision to use new technologies or not. Below, we have analyzed some factors that have been considered to be related to the platform to be developed in CORTEX².

2.1. Perceived control

The concept of perceived control stems from Rotter's social learning theory (Rotter, 1966), which suggests that a person who believes they can control their environment also believes they can control their behavior. Consequently, this factor has been extensively studied in its direct influence on pleasure (Hui & Bateson, 1991), mood, engagement (Ward & Barnes, 2001), satisfaction (Wathieu et al., 2002) and purchase intention (Mathur, 1998).

Likewise, when discussing the use of new technology, appropriate perceived control becomes crucial for the user to decide to learn how to use it. For this purpose, a related factor is usability (Lozada Cantorán et al., 2017).

2.1.1. Usability

Despite the different ways of defining usability, they all aim to measure user satisfaction, their experience, and the ease of using software. To achieve this, various factors are taken into consideration¹:

- Intuitive design: A nearly easy understanding of the architecture and navigation of the software or website.
- Ease of learning: How fast a user who has never seen the user interface before can accomplish basic tasks.
- Efficiency of use: How fast an experienced user can achieve tasks in the system.
- Ability to remember (Memorability): How the user can remember to use the system effectively in future uses.
- Error occurrence and acuteness: The extent to which users make errors while using the software, the severity of the errors, and the extent to which users recover from the errors.

¹ <https://www.usability.gov/what-and-why/usability-evaluation.html>

- User satisfaction: The extent to which the user likes using the system.

A high value in these factors is difficult to guarantee in the early stages of development, but there are different recommendations that can help prevent some future problems. Firstly, the perfect design of the user interface is the ideal and most effective way to achieve high usability, providing user satisfaction, meeting their needs, and enabling them to perform their tasks with ease, enjoyment, and effectiveness. Tawfig et al. suggest that an appropriate way to ensure suitable interfaces is to create samples and mock-ups of different parts of the interface during the design phase and conduct a preliminary study to obtain specifications that satisfy the target user (Tawfig et al., 2016). These samples don't necessarily have to be graphical representations; any method that allows the User Advisory Board to visualize the different components of the interface can be used.

On the other hand, the style to be used throughout the software is crucial (Macleod, 1994). To achieve this, it is recommended to follow the principles of good high-level design. A very clearly and concisely expressed set of such principles can be found in the opening pages of 'Human Interface Guidelines: The Apple Desktop Interface' (Apple Computer, 1987). Further principles, with examples of their use, are given in ISO 9241-110: 2020.

Regardless of the aforementioned recommendations, it is essential to conduct one or more usability studies in more advanced stages of the project to ensure appropriate usability and identify any potential problems that may arise during development. Usability studies provide valuable insights from actual users' interactions with the software, helping to fine-tune the user experience and address any usability issues effectively. By conducting these studies, developers can make informed decisions to improve the software's usability and enhance user satisfaction.

2.1.2. Technofatigue

The adoption of new technologies is not an easy task. Specifically, in communication technologies, users may experience fatigue, anxiety, or concern as a result of excessive use (Wiederhold, 2020). These problems can arise for various reasons:

- **Desynchronization:** Video calls involve synchronized gestures, vocalizations and movements. If this synchronization is disrupted even by a few milliseconds due to technology, our brain unconsciously registers the problem and seeks to restore synchronization.
- **Lack of non-verbal communication:** Real-life conversations include gestures and signals from the whole body. In a video call, these signals and

gestures may be lost, making non-verbal communication in the conversation challenging. Additionally, the problem is exacerbated as communication technologies often include other sources of conversation, such as chat, which can be distracting from this type of communication.

- **Extended person:** Another problem with these technologies is extending the interlocutor to fill the entire screen. This can be intimidating to our brain, generating stress even if we are not consciously aware of it.

Focusing on the use case of video calls and training, the use of Virtual Reality (VR) with full body, hand-tracking, and ways to show emotions in the avatar can mitigate the second and third points by generating greater trust in the interlocutor (Kim et al., 2019; Latoschik et al., 2017; van Loon et al., 2018). Additionally, it is recommended to minimize distractions during conversations by reducing the number of elements that can cause them.

In the case of the first issue, it is worth noting that higher realism of the scene and avatar leads to greater immersion and, therefore, less fatigue (Weech et al., 2019).

While the use of Virtual Environments (VE) can reduce fatigue factors related to video conferencing, it can also lead to increased other fatigue factors. Visual fatigue in VE is mainly caused by the vergence-accommodation conflict (VAC), which is a mismatch between perceived and virtual depth. Motion can also cause fatigue, especially vibrational motion experienced while using helmet-mounted displays (HeMDs) in scenarios like military training on rough terrains. The vibrational motion occurs due to the blur obtained when the eye tries to stabilize in relation to the external environment while the screen moves with the user's head. This motion sickness can be experienced in virtual environments due to visually moving backgrounds without physical movement (cybersickness) or simulated motion (simulator sickness) (Iskander et al., 2018).

Considering this, it is recommended to use static backgrounds with adequate lighting in order to allow users to focus on their interlocutors or the objects they need to visualize without increasing factors that cause dizziness.

These variables that increase fatigue in VE are largely related to the sense of presence. The greater the presence, the less fatigue is experienced, but the more variables that increase fatigue are introduced (Weech et al., 2019). Therefore, striking the right balance is essential. Moreover, this level of fatigue will increase the longer the technology is used. Hence, it would be necessary to include a recommendation to take breaks after certain periods of use, as done in video games, where an alert appears when using VR for an extended time.

To achieve an appropriate balance that reduces the chances of causing dizziness, it is advisable to address this point in a subsequent study, once the platform is in a more advanced stage of development.

Indeed, apart from the factors related to software and technology, there are certain individual characteristics and conditions that can influence fatigue and should be taken into account (Montag et al., 2022):

- **Age, gender, and personality:** Difference in age groups, genders, and personality traits may lead to different experience of fatigue when using new technologies. For example, older individuals may have different cognitive abilities and physical limitations that affect their tolerance to technology usage. Gender differences may also play a role in how fatigue is experienced. Additionally, certain personality traits may influence an individual's response to technology-related fatigue.
- **Previous exhaustion:** Individuals who have experienced previous exhaustion or fatigue, whether due to technological use or other reasons, may be more susceptible to fatigue in future technology interactions.
- **Psychopathies (e.g. depression):** Psychological conditions such as depression and other psychopathies can impact an individual's energy levels, mood, and overall well-being, potentially influencing their response to technology-related fatigue.

Considering these individual factors is important when designing technology and conducting usability studies. It allows for a more comprehensive understanding of how different users may experience and respond to the technology, enabling developers to tailor their solutions and interventions to better meet users' needs and reduce potential negative effects like fatigue.

2.1.3. Technostress

The factor referred to as "technostress" is related to the stress derived from the introduction and use of new technologies, leading to negative psychosocial effects related to the use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT). It involves a poor adaptation to dealing with new technologies in a healthy manner (Tarafdar et al., 2015).

More and more, ICTs have become more present in the work environment, so the technostress caused has been quite studied (Baabdullah et al., 2022; Dragano & Lunau, 2020). The characteristics of ICT that have an impact on technological stress include:

- The presence of excessive notifications, ease of holding meetings, and excessive usage during and outside working hours are features of ICT that can impact technostress. This issue is related to how users use technology and may not be easily avoidable.
- The fear of expending too much effort, time, and cost to learn how to use new software can also contribute to technostress. Ensuring that the software is user-friendly and providing users with a clear understanding of its benefits can help reduce technostress (Tarafdar et al., 2015).

To mitigate technostress caused by the fear of using new technology, it is recommended to ensure that users can easily learn to use the platform and understand its benefits. Some approaches to achieving this are:

- Creating a quick and easy-to-understand user manual.
- Providing easily accessible tutorials within the platform to guide users in their initial steps.
- Allowing users to explore and access most of the tools without delving too deeply.

Regarding the use of AR/VR in the workplace and additional factors influencing technostress, there is less extensive research. One crucial factor is users' perception of data privacy and security concerns related to the platform collecting personal data that could be sold or stolen, such as information used to create avatars or conversations (Adams et al., 2018). Maintaining transparency in data usage and security practices can help alleviate this concern (Chang et al., n.d.; Clothier et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2016).

Another factor that influences the rejection of this technology is how the user is represented in the virtual environment. Avatars used in AR/VR technologies, particularly in the workplace and educational contexts, are expected to have a close-to-reality appearance. However, using hyper-realistic avatars can lead to users not recognizing themselves or feeling insecure when using the software (Thaler et al., 2018). This leads us to ask whether the generated avatar should be allowed to be modified and to what extent it can be modifiable. But, being able to modify it also includes other possible problems, such as "body dysmorphia", where the user may develop other psychological disturbances due to the fact that the user may believe that his/her avatar has a better physical appearance than the one s/he really has.

Due to the limited scope of the studies consulted, which mostly refer to prolonged use of avatars in video games and simulators, further investigation is needed to delve deeper into the issue. In Section 4 of this document, a study is presented that has been conducted to address and clarify these specific points.

Considering the points mentioned earlier, it is essential to consider the level of immersion that the AR/VR system must offer to achieve an adequate "user presence." User presence refers to the user's sense of being physically present in the virtual world, which is crucial for experiencing the benefits expected from using the system.

At first glance, it might be assumed that higher realism in the virtual environment would lead to greater immersion. However, studies indicate that factors such as tracking level (the system's ability to follow the user's movements), stereoscopy (depth perception of the scene), and the user's field of vision have a more significant impact on immersion compared to other characteristics like image quality, resolution, and sound (Cummings & Bailenson, 2015). Moreover, it is essential to consider individual differences and preferences. There may be instances, such as when users have pre-existing pathologies like social phobia or body insecurities, where they prefer less realism in the virtual environment (Oh et al., 2018). Thus, striking the right balance between realism and comfort for users is crucial in designing AR/VR technologies.

Therefore, it is considered necessary to conduct a study to see the appropriate level of quality for the own avatar. The analysis of this point has also been included in the study of section 4.

3. User advisor board

As the platform takes shape, we expect to conduct various studies that will provide us with information on its acceptability, feedback, and potential improvements directly from relevant users.

In Deliverable D5.1, the three case studies of the platform to be developed were described:

- **VR Business Meetings:** The objective of this use case is to build a videoconferencing solution that will bring in technological advances in virtual reality for the context of teleworking. Teleworking is seen as a gain in quality of life because it avoids the often long and tiring journeys. It allows the company to be more agile and efficient because the teams are no longer formed on the basis of geographical proximity but on the basis of adequacy to the objective.
- **VR Remote Training:** The training use case is based on an existing client-solution developed by Actimage which is used for introductory VR trainings on excavators. The current solution, however, only allows a single-user offline training. If the trainee encounters problems during the training or has any questions, it might not be possible for them to get support easily. The goal is to open the VR training environment to other participants, first and foremost a trainer that remotely participates in training classes and can give advice whenever needed.
- **Remotely assisted AR Industrial Maintenance:** This use case describes the use of a MR device by a technician during a maintenance operation of an industrial machine. Three types of actors are involved in the use case, using various devices from different locations. A technician is guided remotely by an expert and a third participant is called to control the maintenance operation via the collaboration space. The scenario implementation will highlight CORTEX² capability to handle 2D and 3D models occurring in heterogeneous devices at the same live session with high quality video rendering under limited network conditions and with the involvement of IoT services.

Each use case requires a different type of role, making it challenging to find target users for all three cases. Therefore, a separate user advisor board is needed for each use case.

3.1. Criteria to be analyzed

Age: There is no specific age criterion to participate in any of the three use cases. However, a minimum age of 18 and a maximum age of 65 are established to gather diverse opinions from a broad range of participants.

Previous knowledge: The level of education is not a significant factor in this project to establish a minimum requirement. However, for each case study, to ensure the users' opinions are relevant, there should be a certain level of experience and prior knowledge for each role as a requirement.

Moreover, since AR/VR is a crucial aspect of CORTEX², it is advisable to have some users with prior experience using this technology. While the expertise of the users is of utmost value, having a portion of familiarity with the technology being used will provide more realistic insights and feedback.

Origin: Including cultural diversity can provide a broader perspective. However, the challenge of including users from different countries lies in the diversity of languages and the difficulty users may face in expressing ideas in a language other than their own. This issue can be addressed by creating multiple user groups, but that increases the complexity of the process. Therefore, it is recommended to minimize the number of groups and ensure that users within the same group share a common language in which they feel comfortable expressing themselves.

Diversity: Apart from considering the origin aspect mentioned earlier, to obtain different viewpoints, it is essential to include diversity in the study. This involves ensuring representation of all roles within each use case. Additionally, efforts should be made to achieve gender parity. Moreover, it is advisable to include users with different abilities to obtain recommendations and advice for achieving the goal of inclusiveness and accessibility.

3.2. Inclusion criteria

- **Age:** 18-65 years old.
- **Previous Knowledge:**
 - VR Business Meetings: Prior experience with business meetings.
 - VR Remote Training: Expert trainers in the relevant fields and students (or former students) with experience in learning and practicing the subject matter.
 - Remotely Assisted AR Industrial Maintenance: Prior experience in industrial machinery maintenance and/or repair.
 - Common: A portion of users in each use case should have experience with AR/VR.
- **Origin:** Users within the same group should feel comfortable using the language employed.
- **Diversity:** Each user advisory group must include:

- Multiple users for each role in the use case.
- Gender parity with a difference of less than 20%.

3.3. Exclusion criteria

- Null or very limited ICT skills.
- Physical or psychological issues that hinder the performance of the corresponding tasks.

4. Preliminary study

4.1. Introduction

While augmented reality integrates virtual and real objects in real-time on a screen, virtual reality allows users to control and navigate their movements in a simulated real or imagined world (Ro et al., 2018; Suh & Prophet, 2018). Both technologies are often combined to induce a more immersive experience (Chuah, 2018).

In such environments, achieving a successful experience is considered dependent on achieving an appropriate level of user presence. In other words, making the user feel transported into the virtual environment (Weech et al., 2019). One of the objectives related to presence is to mitigate the issue of cybersickness. Cybersickness refers to the set of discomfort and malaise symptoms produced by exposure to virtual reality (Stanney & Hash, 1998).

Several factors contribute to the occurrence of cybersickness. Some of them are casual factors (Knight & Arns, 2006; McCauley & Sharkey, 1992; Moss & Muth, 2011; Reason & Brand, 1975; Rebenitsch & Owen, 2016). However, others are related to presence. Weech suggests that certain factors reduce cybersickness and increase presence, such as sensory adjustments and greater interaction. On the other hand, there are also immersion-related factors that increase both cybersickness and presence: expanding the field of view, adding stereoscopy, or providing congruent multisensory information.

Of these factors, increasing control and interaction with the virtual environment can significantly enhance user presence and reduce cybersickness. To achieve this, it is often necessary to include a representation of the user within the environment, allowing them to embody a virtual avatar (Grabarczyk y Pokropski, 2016; Slater et al., 1996).

However, incorporating user avatars in a virtual environment can lead to potential challenges if not done correctly, affecting the overall experience and giving rise to other issues (Aymerich-Franch, 2020). On one hand, using avatars that closely resemble reality can trigger feelings of insecurity while using the tool (Thaler et al., 2018). On the other hand, allowing avatar customization may lead to altered behavior (Yee et al., 2009) or the development of psychological conditions like body dysmorphia (Raman, 2016).

Using avatars that approach reality but do not cross into hyper-realistic territory can help mitigate some of the self-esteem-related problems and avoid insecurity. However, this might also result in a reduction of user presence. Studies agree that factors such as tracking level, stereoscopy, and the user's field of vision have a greater impact on user presence compared to image quality, resolution, and sound (Cummings & Bailenson, 2016).

To explore the advantages of user acceptability and technostress caused by the difference in avatar quality, a study has been conducted. This study analyzed three types of avatars: hyperrealistic, non-realistic, and the use of avatars belonging to others. The goal is to understand the benefits of each type and gather user preferences in different contexts.

4.2. Inclusion criteria

The inclusion/exclusion criteria for users have been derived from the requirements for the user advisory board but adapted to the study. Specifically, the criteria related to the VR Business Meetings use case have been used, with the addition of a criterion for inclusion stating that participants must have experience in online meetings or with VR experience.

Here is a summary of the main criteria:

Inclusion criteria

- Age: 18-65 years old
- Previous Knowledge: Experience with online meetings or VR experience
- Ability to sign the informed consent.

Exclusion criteria

- Null or very limited ICT skills.
- Sensory disorders that make it very difficult to participate in the study (blindness, deafness).
- Inability to read and write in the language available in each country.

4.3. Method

4.3.1. **Participants**

The final sample consisted of a total of 42 participants, 22 men and 20 women. The participants' ages ranged from 22 to 62 years, with a mean age of 32.4 years (SD = 9.3). The literacy level was high, with 71.5% having a university degree or higher, of which 16.7% held a doctorate. The study was conducted in two countries: Spain and Germany. There were 32 participants from Spain (UJI) and 10 from Germany (DFKI).

4.3.2. Software

To simulate the use of an avatar at different levels of quality, the software Video Compression and Alternative Appearance (VCAA) described in the Task 3.2 (Video Compression and Alternative Appearance (VCAA) Documentation) has been utilized. VCAA, through the use of deep learning-based techniques, achieves a significant reduction in bandwidth while maintaining visual fidelity. Moreover, the integration of a generative model as a fundamental component allows the possibility of altering the appearance of the character in the video call.

With VCAA, a real photograph that follows the user's movements can be used to replace the video output. This photograph can have the desired level of quality, including being non-realistic. Therefore, VCAA enables conducting the study with the various required levels and even using photographs that do not correspond to the actual user.

Figure 1: Example of VCAA output. Left: Exit from the camera. Right: Photograph that follows the movements.

4.3.3. Hardware

All users conducted the study individually on a computer with an NVIDIA RTX3060 graphics card through local access. This graphics card enables the execution of the software with minimal delay in the user's image and movements.

4.3.4. Study design

The study consisted of a classic usability test (Nielsen, 1993), in which the VCAA software was used with different photographs. The assessment method employed was task analysis (Redish, 2019), conducted individually. During the test, each user familiarized themselves with the system and followed the researcher's instructions to obtain quantitative data. The study was carried out individually for each participant.

4.4. Variables and measuring instruments

The assessment protocol consisted of three parts:

1. **User Information:** This part collected sociodemographic data and information about the participants' experience with meetings and VR before the task.
2. **Presence Level Measurement:** During each test, the level of presence experienced by the user was evaluated based on their opinion. This assessment aimed to gauge how immersed and engaged the users felt in the virtual environment.
3. **Final Evaluation:** After completing all four tests with different avatar representations, the participants provided their opinions on the experiences. This final evaluation compared the four tests and was also based on the users' opinions.

These three parts of the assessment protocol allowed gathering valuable data on user experiences and preferences with different avatar representations in the virtual environment.

4.4.1. **User profile**

To obtain the user's profile, a series of data was collected before starting the beta test. This data included:

- **Demographic data:** Information such as gender and age.
- **Education level:** Participants' highest level of education achieved.
- **Experience with videoconferences:** Details about the participants' previous experience with videoconferences.
- **Experience with virtual reality:** Information on the participants' prior experience with virtual reality technology.

Collecting this data allowed researchers to understand the background and characteristics of the participants, which can help in analyzing the results and drawing meaningful conclusions from the beta test.

4.4.2. **Measures obtained in each test**

To obtain the measurements regarding the user's opinion at the end of each test, a questionnaire based on a five-point scale that ranges from *Strongly Disagree* to

Strongly Agree adapted from the System Usability Scale (SUS) has been used (Brooke, 1996).

To measure the user's sense of presence in each test, a psychometric approach was used to evaluate the levels of embodiment towards an artificial body part, specifically the face. The latent variables of ownership, agency, and location were identified (Longo et al., 2008). Ownership refers to perceiving the body as one's own, as a source of sensations. Agency is linked to the sensation of control over one's own actions. And location refers to the experience of the self-located in the position of our body. The questions were adapted from a validated test (Roth & Latoschik, 2020), with some modifications to focus solely on the face. Some similar questions were removed to avoid confusion for the users.

Additionally, a section on the sensation of privacy was included, with questions adapted from a validated technostress test (Nimrod, 2018). These privacy-related questions were included in the specific questionnaires for each test as they were considered more relevant in the context of each evaluation.

4.4.3. Measures obtained in the post evaluation

The post-evaluation consists of three parts. The first part aims to assess the technostress produced by the use of avatars. This questionnaire utilizes the same scale as the individual tests (SUS). The questions have been extracted and adapted from a validated technostress questionnaire (Feng & Bourazzouq, 2021).

The second part seeks to understand the user's preferences regarding the avatar to be used in different situations. The questionnaire includes eight situations related to work, education, or leisure. For each situation, multiple responses can be selected.

Lastly, the third part is an acceptability test to determine the perceived usefulness and intention to use. The scale used is again the SUS scale, and the questions have been extracted and adapted from a validated acceptability questionnaire (Castilla et al., 2016, 2018, 2020).

By utilizing these post-evaluation questionnaires, the researchers aimed to gather comprehensive feedback from the participants on technostress, avatar preferences, and the perceived usefulness of the system, allowing for a thorough analysis of the user experience and acceptability of the different avatar representations in various scenarios.

4.5. Procedure

The study for each user was conducted in the following phases:

1. **PRE-Assessment:** In this phase, the user was informed about the study and what they would be doing. If they agreed to participate, they signed the informed consent document.
2. **PRE-Questionnaire:** The user's sociodemographic data and profile were collected in this phase.
3. **Study (first part):** Three tests were conducted in a single session, with each test using a different photograph. Each user always performed the four tests in the same order to avoid any impact related to differences in the sequence. In each test, the following steps were carried out.
 - a. Avatar description: The user was provided with an explanation of the type of avatar being used, which included three options:
 - **Hyper-realistic:** A digitally created representation of a human being with an exceptionally high level of detail and realism.
 - **Not realistic:** A digital representation of a human being intentionally deviating from realistic appearance and features, adopting stylized or abstract styles.
 - **Another person:** A Hyper-realistic digital representation of another person who is not the user.
 - b. Familiarization: The user became acquainted with the avatar by performing head movements and gestures for 15 to 30 seconds.
 - c. Interview: The researcher simulated an interview with the user, asking personal questions. The user had the option to decline to answer, and if they felt uncomfortable, they could request a change of question. The objective was to encourage conversation, divert attention from the avatar, and observe its movements during responses for 1 to 2 minutes.
 - d. Questionnaire: While the researcher prepared for the next experiment, the user completed the corresponding questionnaire.
4. **Study (second part):** For the final test, the camera captured the interviewer's movements using the hyper-realistic photograph of the user. This way, the user could see how another person was using their own avatar. The data collection process remained the same as in the first part, using the interview format. Finally, the user responded to a fourth questionnaire.
5. **POST-Study:** Finally, the user completed the POST-Study questionnaire.

4.6. Protocol and documents

Due to the study being conducted in two countries by different researchers, a protocol was created to ensure consistency during the sessions. This protocol

document includes an explanation of the study and the different types of avatars used. It also outlines the steps to be followed in each test and provides example questions to guide the researchers during the sessions while engaging in conversation with the users as they interact with the avatars.

To facilitate the execution of the study, a ready-to-print protocol (ANNEX B: Study protocol) was developed. This document follows the following structure:

- Consent form and confidentiality note.
- Pre-Study questionnaire measures.
- Post-Test Questionnaire for each test.
- Post-Study Questionnaire.

Study execution

The study was executed throughout June 2023 by researchers from UJI and DFKI, ensuring that the protocol was consistently followed across both locations, and the data collected would be comparable and suitable for analysis.

Figure 2: Users during the study at UJI.

Figure 3: Users during the study at DFKI.

4.7. Results

This section collects the results obtained. These results have been obtained from the questionnaires completed during the session. The results have been divided into different sections:

- Participants
- Measures during the tests.
- Post study measures

In addition, an analysis of these results is included. At the end of this section, conclusions that evaluate these results globally are included.

4.7.1. Participants

The final sample consisted of a total of 42 participants, 22 men and 20 women. The age ranged from 22 to 62 years, with a mean of 32.4 years (SD = 9.3). The study was conducted in two countries: Spain (UJI) and Germany (DFKI). 32 participants were from Spain, and 10 were from Germany.

Table 1 summarizes the sociodemographic characteristics of the participants.

	UJI	DFKI	ALL
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User number (sex)	32 (19 w, 13 m)	10 (1 w, 9 m)	42 (20 w, 22 m)
Average age	33,7 (SD: 10)	28,6 (SD: 3,2)	32,4 (SD: 9,3)
Studies level	P: 3,2%; S: 28,2%; U: 21,8%; M: 21,8%; D: 25%	P: 0%; S: 10%; U: 10%; M: 80%; D: 0%	P: 2,4%; S: 23,8%; U: 19,1%; M: 35,7%; D: 19,1%

Table 1: Sociodemographic characteristics of the participants. P=Primary, S= Secondary, U= University, M=Master, D=Doctorate.

4.7.2. Videoconference experience

Experience with video conferences is important in the study as it may influence the results. Table 2 contains the users' experience in work-related, educational, and leisure video conferences. The total percentage of experience is also included at the end, regardless of the specific usage context.

	UJI	DFKI	ALL
Q1: How many times have you held a video conference related to your work?			
Never	3,1 %	-	2,4 %
1 time	-	-	-
2 to 10 times	25 %	10 %	21,4 %
More than 10 times	21,9 %	0 %	16,7 %
Frequently	50 %	90 %	59,5 %
Q2: How many times have you held a video conference that is related to education (Giving or receiving classes)?			
Never	21,9 %	-	16,7 %
1 time	-	10 %	2,4 %
2 to 10 times	15,6 %	20 %	16,7 %
More than 10 times	37,5 %	40 %	38 %
Frequently	25 %	30 %	26,2 %
Q3: How many times have you held a video conference that is not related to your job or education?			
Never	12,5 %	30 %	16,7 %
1 time	9,4 %	-	7,1 %
2 to 10 times	28,1 %	20 %	26,2 %
More than 10 times	15,6 %	20 %	16,7 %
Frequently	34,4 %	30 %	33,3 %
General experience with online meetings			

Never	-	-	-
1 time	-	-	-
2 to 10 times	-	-	-
More than 10 times	37,5 %	10 %	31 %
Frequently	62,5 %	90 %	69 %

Table 2: Experience in videoconferencing of users. Questions Q1 to Q3.

As seen in the table, nearly 70% of users have high experience in videoconferences, while the remaining users have used them more than 10 times.

4.7.3. Experience in Virtual reality

Experience with virtual reality devices and virtual environments can be a factor that influences the users' opinions on avatars. Table 3 contains this information, divided into general experience and specific experience in work-related, educational, and leisure contexts. Additionally, it includes whether the user has access to any virtual reality devices.

	UJI	DFKI	ALL
Q4: How many times have you used a reality virtual system before today?			
Never	15,6 %	10 %	14,3 %
1 time	12,5 %	40 %	19 %
2 to 10 times	43,8 %	30 %	40,5 %
More tan 10 times	-	10 %	2,4 %
Frequently	28,1 %	10 %	23,8 %
Q5: How many times have you used a virtual reality system at work (for example a meeting)?			
Never	62,5 %	70 %	64,3 %
1 time	3,1 %	20 %	7,1 %
2 to 10 times	9,4 %	10 %	9,6 %
More tan 10 times	9,4 %	-	7,1 %
Frequently	15,6 %	-	11,9 %
Q6: How many times have you used a virtual reality system in education?			
Never	75 %	90 %	78,6 %
1 time	9,4 %	-	7,1 %
2 to 10 times	15,6 %	10 %	14,3 %
More tan 10 times	-	-	-
Frequently	-	-	-
Q7: How many times have you used a virtual reality system in leisure (games, meetings, social events...)?			
Never	28,1 %	40 %	30,1 %
1 time	15,7 %	10 %	14,2 %

2 to 10 times	34,3 %	40 %	35,7 %
More tan 10 times	6,2 %	10 %	7,1 %
Frequently	15,7 %	-	11,9 %
Q8: Do you have any virtual reality devices at home?			
Yes	21,8 %	10 %	19 %
No	78,2 %	90 %	81 %

Table 3: Virtual reality experience of the users. Questions Q4 to Q8.

The data in table 3 indicate that more than 66% of users have experience with VR, 23% frequently. However, only 28.6% have used VR at work, and 14,3% in education. Most of them, 54,7% have use VR in a leisure context. Later we will use this information to relate the answers of the user with this factor.

4.7.4. Measures during the tests

At the end of each test, the users completed a questionnaire regarding the type of avatar used. The questions in this questionnaire pertain to the sense of presence and can be categorized into three parts: ownership, agency, and location. Table 4, Table 5 and Table 7 present the data obtained for the three types of avatars. Additionally, Table 8 displays the results obtained from the privacy-related questions, which also include the final test where the user's avatar is controlled by another person.

Property

Table 4 displays the results obtained for the avatar ownership factor (property), for each type of avatar evaluated.

		Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither disagree, nor agree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
Q9: It felt like the virtual face was my face.						
UJI	Hyper-realistic	-	15.6 %	3.1 %	68.8 %	12.5 %
	Other person	65.6 %	25 %	3.1 %	6.3 %	-
	Non-realistic	-	21.9 %	21.9 %	46.9 %	9.4 %
DFKI	Hyper-realistic	-	-	20 %	50 %	30 %
	Other person	60 %	20 %	-	-	20 %
	Non-realistic	10 %	30 %	20 %	30 %	10 %
ALL	Hyper-realistic	-	11.9 %	7.1 %	64.3 %	16.7 %

	Other person	64.3 %	23.8 %	2.4 %	4.8 %	4.8 %
	Non-realistic	2.4 %	23.8 %	21.4 %	42.9 %	9.5 %
Q10: The virtual face felt like a human face						
UJI	Hyper-realistic	-	12.5	9.4	56.3	21.9
	Other person	12.5 %	18.8	9.4	31.3	28.1
	Non-realistic	6.3 %	18.8	25.0	34.4	15.6
DFKI	Hyper-realistic	-	10.0	30.0	30.0	30.0
	Other person	-	10.0	10.0	40.0	40.0
	Non-realistic	20 %	30.0	30.0	20.0	
ALL	Hyper-realistic	-	11.9	14.3	50.0	23.8
	Other person	9.5 %	16.7	9.5	33.3	31.0
	Non-realistic	9.5 %	21.4	26.2	31.0	11.9
Q11: I had the feeling that the virtual face belonged to me						
UJI	Hyper-realistic	-	3.1 %	25 %	43.8 %	28.1 %
	Other person	37.5 %	28.1 %	9.4 %	15.6 %	9.4 %
	Non-realistic	9.4 %	25 %	18.8 %	34.4 %	12.5 %
DFKI	Hyper-realistic	-	-	20 %	40 %	40 %
	Other person	60 %	20 %	-	10 %	10 %
	Non-realistic	10 %	20 %	20 %	40 %	10 %
ALL	Hyper-realistic	-	2.4 %	23.8 %	42.9 %	31 %
	Other person	42.9 %	26.2 %	7.1 %	14.3 %	9.5 %
	Non-realistic	9.5 %	23.8 %	19 %	35.7 %	11.9 %

Table 4: Answers to questions regarding the Property factor. Questions Q9 to Q11.

To check if there is any relationship between the results of the avatar agency sensation and demographic data and previous experience, a Spearman correlation analysis was conducted. All the results have a correlation below 0.25 with a high error. Therefore, it is considered that there is almost no correlation between this data. This means that this factor is not determined by previous experience or demographic data.

Next, the results obtained for the agency factor are presented. These results are shown in Table 5.

		Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither disagree, nor agree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
Q12: The movements of the virtual face seemed to be my own movements						
UJI	Hyper-realistic	3.1 %	28.1 %	28.1 %	40.6 %	-
	Other person	9.4 %	15.6 %	18.8 %	50 %	6.3 %
	Non-realistic	-	15.6 %	21.9 %	18.8 %	43.8 %
DFKI	Hyper-realistic	-	10 %	30 %	50 %	10 %
	Other person	-	10 %	10 %	40 %	40 %
	Non-realistic	-	10 %	10 %	50 %	30 %
ALL	Hyper-realistic	2.4 %	23.8 %	28.6 %	42.9 %	2.4 %
	Other person	7.1 %	14.3 %	16.7 %	47.6 %	14.3 %
	Non-realistic	-	14.3 %	19 %	26.2 %	40.5 %
Q13: I enjoyed controlling the virtual face						
UJI	Hyper-realistic	3.1 %	3.1 %	21.9 %	31.3 %	40.6 %
	Other person	-	18.8 %	34.4 %	31.3 %	15.6 %
	Non-realistic	-	-	3.1 %	37.5 %	59.4 %
DFKI	Hyper-realistic	-	-	-	40 %	60 %
	Other person	-	10 %	10 %	30 %	50 %
	Non-realistic	-	-	20 %	10 %	70 %
ALL	Hyper-realistic	2.4 %	2.4 %	16.7 %	33.3 %	45.2 %
	Other person	-	16.7 %	28.6 %	31 %	23.8 %
	Non-realistic	-	-	7.1 %	31 %	61.9 %
Q14: I have felt comfortable using the virtual face.						
UJI	Hyper-realistic	3.1 %	3.1 %	15.6 %	6.3 %	62.5 %
	Other person	3.1 %	3.1 %	28.1 %	18.8 %	28.1 %
	Non-realistic	-	-	9.4 %	31.3 %	56.3 %
DFKI	Hyper-realistic	-	-	40 %	10 %	40 %
	Other person	-	-	50 %	20 %	30 %
	Non-realistic	-	-	30 %	30 %	30 %
ALL	Hyper-realistic	2.4 %	2.4 %	21.4 %	7.1 %	57.1 %
	Other person	2.4 %	2.4 %	33.3 %	19 %	28.6 %
	Non-realistic	-	-	14.3 %	31 %	50 %
Q15: I felt as if I was causing the movement of the virtual face.						
UJI	Hyper-realistic	-	6.3 %	6.3 %	37.5 %	50 %
	Other person	-	6.3 %	12.5 %	53.1 %	28.1 %
	Non-realistic	-	-	15.6 %	31.3 %	53.1 %
DFKI	Hyper-realistic	-	-	-	50 %	50 %
	Other person	-	10 %	-	50 %	40 %
	Non-realistic	-	-	20 %	40 %	40 %

ALL	Hyper-realistic	-	4.8 %	4.8 %	40.5 %	50 %
	Other person	-	7.1 %	9.5 %	52.4 %	31 %
	Non-realistic	-	-	7.1 %	31 %	61.9 %
Q16: The movements of the virtual face were synchronous with my own movements.						
UJI	Hyper-realistic	-	18.8 %	18.8 %	28.1 %	34.4 %
	Other person	3.1 %	12.5 %	15.6 %	34.4 %	34.4 %
	Non-realistic	3.1 %	9.4 %	15.6 %	34.4 %	37.5 %
DFKI	Hyper-realistic	-	20 %	20 %	40 %	20 %
	Other person	-	20 %	-	60 %	20 %
	Non-realistic	-	10 %	40 %	20 %	30 %
ALL	Hyper-realistic	-	19 %	19 %	31 %	31 %
	Other person	2.4 %	14.3 %	11.9 %	40.5 %	31 %
	Non-realistic	-	14.3 %	19 %	26.2 %	40.5 %

Table 5: Answers to the questions regarding the Agency factor. Questions Q12 to Q16.

Regarding the agency factor, the same correlation analysis was performed. The results, shown in Table 6, do not show correlation with age, gender, level of education, or previous experience in online meetings. However, there is a correlation with previous experience in virtual reality.

	r_s	p
Hyper-realistic	0.469	0.002
Other person	0,411	0,007
Non-Realistic	0,329	0,003

Table 6: Correlation between Agency and RV experience.

The correlation indicates that the more a user is familiar with virtual reality, the greater sense of control they will have, and therefore, they will experience a higher level of presence.

Moving on to the next factor, which is the feeling of transformation, this refers to feeling that one's own body is different when using an avatar. The results are shown in Table 7.

		Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither disagree, nor agree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
Q17: I had the illusion of owning a different face from my own.						
UJI	Hyper-realistic	6.3 %	34.4 %	21.9 %	37.5 %	-
	Other person	6.3 %	9.4 %	9.4 %	28.1 %	46.9 %

	Non-realistic	3.1 %	12.5 %	21.9 %	43.8 %	18.8 %
DFKI	Hyper-realistic	20 %	40 %	20 %	10 %	10 %
	Other person	30 %	20 %	10 %	30 %	10 %
	Non-realistic	40 %	-	10 %	50 %	-
ALL	Hyper-realistic	9.5 %	35.7 %	21.4 %	31 %	2.4 %
	Other person	11.9 %	11.9 %	9.5 %	28.6 %	38.1 %
	Non-realistic	11.9 %	9.5 %	19 %	45.2 %	14.3 %
Q18: I felt the need to check if my face really still looked like what I had in mind.						
UJI	Hyper-realistic	46.9 %	12.5 %	6.3 %	25 %	9.4 %
	Other person	43.8 %	28.1 %	12.5 %	6.3 %	9.4 %
	Non-realistic	37.5 %	21.9 %	18.8 %	12.5 %	9.4 %
DFKI	Hyper-realistic	20 %	40 %	10 %	30 %	-
	Other person	40 %	20 %	30 %	-	10 %
	Non-realistic	30 %	50 %	10 %	-	10 %
ALL	Hyper-realistic	40.5 %	19 %	7.1 %	26.2 %	7.1 %
	Other person	42.9 %	26.2 %	16.7 %	4.8 %	9.5 %
	Non-realistic	35.7 %	28.6 %	16.7 %	9.5 %	9.5 %
Q19: I felt as if the form or appearance of my face had changed.						
UJI	Hyper-realistic	50 %	-	21.9 %	18.8 %	9.4 %
	Other person	37.5 %	3.1 %	3.1 %	15.6 %	40.6 %
	Non-realistic	31.3 %	6.3 %	6.3 %	40.6 %	15.6 %
DFKI	Hyper-realistic	10 %	30 %	10 %	50 %	-
	Other person	40 %	-	50 %	-	10 %
	Non-realistic	-	60 %	10 %	10 %	20 %
ALL	Hyper-realistic	40.5 %	7.1 %	19 %	26.2 %	7.1 %
	Other person	38.1 %	2.4 %	14.3 %	11.9 %	33.3 %
	Non-realistic	23.8 %	19 %	7.1 %	33.3 %	16.7 %

Table 7: Answers to the questions regarding the Change factor. Questions Q17 to Q19.

As with the other two factors, Spearman correlation was analyzed to determine if there is a relationship between the feeling of transformation and sociocultural data and previous experience. The results indicate a non-significant correlation,

suggesting that, similar to the factor of ownership, this data does not significantly influence the feeling of transformation.

Figure 4: Comparison of the presence factors according to the type of avatar.

In Figure 4 the comparison between the mean of all questions for each factor with the type of avatar can be seen. It shows that the feeling of ownership is considerably higher for a hyper-realistic avatar (2.9), lower for a non-realistic avatar (2.2), and significantly lower for an avatar that does not resemble the user (1.5). On the other hand, the sense of control is relatively similar across the three avatars (3, 3.1, 2.7), with a slight decrease in the third case, but not significantly different.

Finally, the factor of transformation is low for a hyper-realistic avatar (1.3), indicating that users felt less of a change in their body with this avatar. This factor increases by the same value for the other two types of avatars (1.9).

Privacy

Table 8 displays the results obtained for the feeling of lack of privacy factor. This table includes the results obtained in the test where another person used the hyper-realistic avatar of the user.

		Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither disagree, nor agree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
Q20: I feel that the use of this type of avatar is an intrusion into my privacy.						
UJI	Hyper-realistic	87.5 %	9.4 %	3.1 %	-	-
	Other person	93.8 %	-	6.3 %	-	-
	Non-realistic	96.9 %	3.1 %	-	-	-

	Impersonation	43.8 %	9.4 %	25 %	12.5 %	9.4 %
DFKI	Hyper-realistic	50 %	20 %	-	30 %	-
	Other person	60 %	20 %	10 %	10 %	-
	Non-realistic	50 %	20 %	10 %	10 %	10 %
	Impersonation	50 %	3.1 %	6.3 %	34.4 %	6.3 %
ALL	Hyper-realistic	78.6 %	11.9 %	2.4 %	7.1 %	-
	Other person	85.7 %	4.8 %	7.1 %	2.4 %	-
	Non-realistic	85.7 %	7.1 %	2.4 %	2.4 %	2.4 %
	Impersonation	45.2 %	7.1 %	23.8 %	11.9 %	11.9 %
Q21: I feel that this kind of avatar reveals private personal information without my consent.						
UJI	Hyper-realistic	81.3 %	18.8 %	-	-	-
	Other person	87.5 %	6.3 %	6.3 %	-	-
	Non-realistic	96.9 %	3.1 %	-	-	-
	Impersonation	50 %	-	20 %	10 %	20 %
DFKI	Hyper-realistic	40 %	30 %	10 %	20 %	-
	Other person	60 %	20 %	10 %	10 %	-
	Non-realistic	50 %	20 %	-	30 %	-
	Impersonation	40 %	-	20 %	30 %	10 %
ALL	Hyper-realistic	71.4 %	21.4 %	2.4 %	4.8 %	-
	Other person	81 %	9.5 %	7.1 %	2.4 %	-
	Non-realistic	85.7 %	7.1 %	-	7.1 %	-
	Impersonation	47.6 %	2.4 %	9.5 %	33.3 %	7.1 %

Table 8: Results to the privacy questions. Questions Q20 to Q21.

Figure 5 presents a visual comparison of the results obtained. As can be seen, the overall feeling of lack of privacy is low (<0.4). However, it increases in the fourth test, where another person used the user's avatar (1.4).

Figure 5: Comparison between the privacy results.

The results are lower than expected. Therefore, a Spearman correlation analysis was conducted to check for any relationship with the previous data. On one hand, it was found that, similar to the previous analyses, there is no correlation with demographic data or prior experience. However, on the other hand, there is some correlation with the data related to presence. These correlation results are shown in Table 9 and Table 10.

	Property		Agency		Change	
	r_s	p	r_s	p	r_s	p
Hyper-realistic	0,289	0,04	0,377	0,014	0,575	0,001
Other person	0,327	0,034	0,323	0,037	0,357	0,02
Non-realistic	0,237	0,1	0,06	0,7	0,354	0,042

Table 9: Correlation between the results in privacy and the presence factors.

Table 9 shows the relationship between the privacy results of each type of avatar and their presence factors. As seen, the overall correlation is relatively low but significant. The noteworthy data are the highest correlation with the change factor for the hyper-realistic avatar ($r=0.575$, $p=0.001$) and the non-significant correlation of the non-realistic avatar with the agency factor ($r=0.06$, $p=0.7$).

The conclusions drawn from this data are that the more an avatar resembles the user, the greater the fear of privacy loss. Additionally, when using another person's avatar, this fear also becomes relevant.

Furthermore, a correlation analysis was conducted between the presence values of the different avatar types and the privacy results from the fourth test. Table 10 displays the results. These findings indicate no correlation with the non-realistic avatar or when using another person's avatar. However, there is a small correlation with the presence obtained when using an avatar that looks like the user, which confirms the results in table 9.

	Property		Agency		Change	
	r_s	p	r_s	p	r_s	p
Hyper-realistic	0,047	0,76	0,355	0,02	0,273	0,031
Other person	0,150	0,3	0,9	0,5	0,1	0,5
Non-realistic	0,158	0,3	-0,273	0,4	-0,18	0,9

Table 10: Correlation between the privacy result of the fourth test and the presence factors.

4.7.5. Measures POST-Study

Next, the results obtained from the questionnaire that the users completed at the end of the study will be presented and analyzed. This questionnaire is divided into three parts: Technostress, avatar preference, and feasibility.

Technostress

	UJI	DFKI	ALL
Q22: Do you feel or would you feel pressured or stressed about maintaining a "perfect" image or appearance through your avatar?			
Less Agree	25 %	10 %	21.4 %
	37.5 %	30 %	35.7 %
	12.5 %	30 %	16.7 %
	25 %	20 %	23.8 %
More Agree	-	10 %	2.4 %
Q23: Do you feel or think you would feel anxiety or stress when comparing your avatar to other people's avatars in virtual environments?			
Less Agree	12.5 %	20 %	14.3 %
	50 %	10 %	40.5 %
	9.4 %	40 %	16.7 %
	28.1 %	30 %	28.6 %
More Agree	-	-	-
Q24: Do you experience or think that you would experience difficulties in expressing your true identity or personality through your avatar?			

Less Agree	65.6 %	-	50 %
	18.8 %	10 %	16.7 %
	3.1 %	20 %	7.1 %
	3.1 %	50 %	14.3 %
More Agree	9.4 %	20 %	11.9 %
Q25: Do you or would you feel uncomfortable or stressed about the lack of privacy or the potential exposure of your real identity while using an avatar?			
Less Agree	53.1 %	30 %	47.6 %
	31.3 %	20 %	28.6 %
	3.1 %	20 %	7.1 %
	9.4 %	20 %	11.9 %
More Agree	3.1 %	10 %	4.8 %
Q26: Do you feel or think you would feel that using avatars in virtual environments exhausts you emotionally or mentally?			
Less Agree	56.3 %	30 %	50 %
	34.4 %	30 %	33.3 %
	6.3 %	30 %	11.9 %
	3.1 %	10 %	4.8 %
More Agree	-	-	-
Q27: Do you experience or think you would experience worries or stress related to the possibility of your avatar being judged or discriminated against by other users?			
Less Agree	34.4 %	40 %	35.7 %
	28.1 %	30 %	28.6 %
	21.9 %	10 %	19 %
	15.6 %	10 %	14.3 %
More Agree	-	10 %	2.4 %
Q28: Do you feel or think that you would feel that the use of avatars in virtual environments negatively affects your self-esteem or self-confidence?			
Less Agree	34.4 %	40 %	35.7 %
	50 %	30 %	45.2 %
	9.4 %	30 %	14.3 %
	3.1 %	-	2.4 %
More Agree	3.1 %	-	2.4 %

Table 11: Results of the technostress questions. Questions Q22 to Q28.

Table 11 presents the results obtained for each question. Overall, the technostress caused by the use of avatars is low. Figure 6 provides a more visual comparison of the responses to the seven questions.

Figure 6: Comparison between the technostress questions.

Questions 25, 26, and 28 have the lowest values of technostress (<1), which pertain to privacy, fatigue, and self-esteem when using avatars. On the other hand, questions 22 and 23 have higher values (>1.5), which are related to the appearance of the avatar.

These results indicate that the use of avatars by itself does not generate a high level of technostress. However, the correlation of these results with certain factors will be analyzed next using Spearman's correlation.

	Gender		Age		Videoconference experience	
	r_s	p	r_s	p	r_s	p
Q22	0,126	0,4	-0,291	0,05	0,068	0,6
Q23	-0,041	0,8	-0,266	0,08	-0,11	0,5
Q24	-0,42	0,5	-0,351	0,042	0,377	0,014
Q25	0,019	0,9	-0,357	0,02	0,12	0,4
Q26	0,096	0,5	-0,332	0,032	-0,1	0,6
Q27	0,359	0,05	-0,183	0,2	0,11	0,48
Q28	0,298	0,018	-0,42	0,8	0,08	0,6

Table 12: Correlation between technostress questions and sociodemographic data.

Table 12 presents the correlation between the result of each technostress question and the sociodemographic and experience data that showed significant results: age, gender, and experience with videoconferences. The results indicate that:

- There is a relationship between questions 27 and 28 with gender. This indicates that women are more concerned about their avatar being judged or discriminated against and how it may affect their self-esteem. This finding is consistent with other studies conducted on appearance in videoconferences (Stewart & Stapleton, 2022). However, this factor may be related to individuals with higher appearance-related anxiety rather than solely gender-related (Levinson & Rodebaugh, 2015; Seekis et al., 2020).
- Questions 22 to 26 are related to age. These questions pertain to the avatar's appearance, privacy, and fatigue while using avatars. A negative correlation suggests that younger participants are more concerned about these factors. This result aligns with existing literature (Stewart & Stapleton, 2022).
- Experience with videoconferences is related to the question about concern for expressing their true personality. The more experience participants have, the greater the concern.

	Property		Agency		Change		Privacy	
	r_s	p	r_s	p	r_s	p	r_s	p
Q22	-0,425	0,005	-0,240	0,125	-0,137	0,1	0,119	0,4
Q23	-0,001	0,9	0,212	0,17	-0,18	0,2	0,053	0,7
Q24	-0,436	0,04	-0,123	0,4	0,26	0,08	0,294	0,06
Q25	-0,305	0,049	-0,49	0,7	0,488	0,001	0,460	0,002
Q26	-0,124	0,4	-0,237	0,13	-0,145	0,3	0,126	0,4
Q27	0,007	0,9	-0,268	0,08	0,001	0,9	0,170	0,28
Q28	0,045	0,7	-0,112	0,5	-0,215	0,17	0,05	0,7

Table 13: Correlation between technostress questions, presence factors and privacy.

Table 13 presents the relationship between the presence factors and technostress. The results indicate, on one hand, that the ownership factor negatively affects questions 22, 23, and 25. In other words, the higher the sense of ownership, the lower the concern about the avatar's appearance and privacy.

On the other hand, it can be observed that the greater the sense of bodily change with the avatar, the higher the concern about privacy. Additionally, the higher the sense of lack of privacy, the greater the fear associated with it.

These findings confirm the theory that increasing presence reduces technostress. Moreover, it specifies that the most important factors are increasing the sense of

ownership of the avatar, reducing the sense of bodily change, and minimizing the sense of lack of privacy.

Avatar preferences

To understand the users' preferences regarding the type of avatar they prefer, different scenarios with multiple responses were proposed. Table 14 displays the obtained results.

	UJI	DFKI	ALL
Q29: Working meeting with your team.			
Hyper-realistic	87.5 %	10 %	69 %
Realistic	18.7 %	80 %	33.3 %
Non-realistic	15.6 %	10 %	14.3 %
Other person	-	10 %	2.4 %
Q30: Working meeting with clients or partners.			
Hyper-realistic	87.5 %	40 %	76.2 %
Realistic	12.5 %	60 %	23.8 %
Non-realistic	9.37 %	10 %	9.5 %
Other person	-	-	-
Q31: Working meeting with senior positions (managers, project managers...).			
Hyper-realistic	90.6 %	40 %	78.6 %
Realistic	9.3 %	50 %	21.4 %
Non-realistic	9.3 %	20 %	11.9 %
Other person	-	-	-
Q32: Education: Attending a class			
Hyper-realistic	25 %	30 %	26.2 %
Realistic	34.3 %	40 %	40.5 %
Non-realistic	43.7 %	30 %	42.9 %
Other person	3.1 %	10 %	2.4 %
Q33: Education: Teaching a class			
Hyper-realistic	59.3 %	10 %	47.6 %
Realistic	25 %	80 %	42.9 %
Non-realistic	6.2 %	10 %	9.5 %
Other person	6.2 %	10 %	4.8 %
Q34: Leisure: Games where you interact with other players.			
Hyper-realistic	-	20 %	4.8 %
Realistic	50 %	30 %	45.2 %
Non-realistic	65.6 %	50 %	52.4 %
Other person	34.3 %	10 %	16.7 %
Q35: Leisure: Meeting with Friends			
Hyper-realistic	43.7 %	40 %	42.9 %

Realistic	43.7 %	30 %	38.1 %
Non-realistic	40.6 %	30 %	28.6 %
Other person	9.3 %	-	7.1 %
Q36: Leisure: Social event (for example a talk)			
Hyper-realistic	31.2 %	40 %	33.3 %
Realistic	46.8 %	40 %	45.2 %
Non-realistic	25 %	20 %	28.6 %
Other person	28.1 %	-	9.5 %

Table 14: Avatar preference of users according to different situations. Questions Q29 to Q36.

Figure 7, Figure 8 and Figure 9 depict the graphical representation of this data for a more visual comparison.

Figure 7: A comparison of work situations.

In the workplace setting, as seen in Figure 7, users prefer to use avatars of themselves and with the highest image quality possible. This preference increases with the seriousness of the meetings. It reaches its peak with the presence of top-level executives (78.6%) and its lowest with the team members (69%).

Figure 8: A comparison of educational situations.

In the educational context, when it comes to the teacher, the same preference as in the workplace setting is observed. That is, users prefer an avatar of themselves with good image quality. However, in this case, the preference between hyper-realistic (47.6%) and realistic (42.9%) avatars is closer. But as students, the preference changes, still preferring an avatar of themselves, but the need for realism is not as high. Thus, the non-realistic avatar (42.9%) and the realistic avatar (40.5%) are preferred over a hyper-realistic avatar (26.2%).

Figure 9: Comparison of leisure situations.

However, for leisure activities, preferences change, and they also vary depending on the type of leisure. For socializing with friends or attending events, users prefer an avatar with good image quality. But in a setting where they have to interact with

both friends and strangers, such as in games, users prefer non-realistic avatars (52.4%).

Feasibility

The final section of the questionnaire aims to assess the perceived usefulness and intention to use avatars in work, education, and leisure settings. Table 15 presents the results obtained.

	UJI	DFKI	ALL
Q37: I find it useful to use an avatar in a work meeting.			
Strongly disagree	15.6 %	20 %	16.7 %
Somewhat disagree	6.3 %	10 %	7.1 %
Neither disagree, nor agree	9.4 %	30 %	14.3 %
Somewhat agree	62.5 %	30 %	54.8 %
Strongly agree	6.3 %	10 %	7.1 %
Q38: I find it useful to use an avatar in education.			
Never	3.1 %	10 %	4.8 %
Strongly disagree	9.4 %	30 %	14.3 %
Somewhat disagree	21.9 %	-	16.7 %
Neither disagree, nor agree	56.3 %	40 %	52.4 %
Somewhat agree	9.4 %	20 %	11.9 %
Q39: I consider it useful to use an avatar in leisure applications.			
Strongly disagree	-	-	-
Somewhat disagree	-	10 %	2.4 %
Neither disagree, nor agree	6.3 %	10 %	7.1 %
Somewhat agree	43.8 %	40 %	42.9 %
Strongly agree	50 %	40 %	47.6 %
Q40: In the future I would be willing to use an avatar in a work meeting.			
Strongly disagree	6.3 %	20 %	9.5 %
Somewhat disagree	9.4 %	20 %	11.9 %
Neither disagree, nor agree	9.4 %	20 %	11.9 %
Somewhat agree	28.1 %	40 %	31 %
Strongly agree	46.9 %	-	35.7 %
Q41: In the future I would be willing to use an avatar in education.			
Strongly disagree	6.3 %	10 %	7.1 %
Somewhat disagree	6.3 %	20 %	9.5 %
Neither disagree, nor agree	9.4 %	-	7.1 %
Somewhat agree	37.5 %	40 %	38.1 %
Strongly agree	40.6 %	30 %	38.1 %
Q42: In the future I would be willing to use an avatar in leisure applications.			
Strongly disagree	-	-	-

Somewhat disagree	-	10 %	2.4 %
Neither disagree, nor agree	-	10 %	2.4 %
Somewhat agree	25 %	30 %	26.2 %
Strongly agree	75 %	50 %	69 %

Table 15: Results of the questions of utility and intention of use. Questions Q37 to Q42.

As Figure 10 shows, users perceive the use of avatars in all three settings (work, education, and leisure) as useful (rated above 2 on the scale) and express a favorable intention to use them (rated above 2.5 on the scale).

Figure 10: Comparison between perceived utility and intention of use.

To identify the factors influencing users' willingness to use a system with avatars, a Spearman correlation analysis was conducted. First, the analysis was performed with previous experience and demographic data. The only significant correlation was found with previous experience in virtual reality. Table 16 shows that this prior experience correlates similarly across all three settings (work, education, and leisure).

	VR experience	
	r_s	p
Q40	0,397	0,009
Q41	0,399	0,009
Q42	0,339	0,009

Table 16: Correlation between the questions of intention of use and experience in virtual reality.

Secondly, the analysis was performed with the presence factors. The property factor was found to be significant for considering the use of avatars in work and education

as useful and also influenced the intention to use them. The results are shown in Table 17.

	Property	
	r_s	p
Q37	0,446	0,003
Q38	0,312	0,048
Q40	0,640	0,001
Q41	0,336	0,029

Table 17: Correlation between the work and education questions with the presence property factor.

Finally, the correlation between the intention to use and the perceived usefulness was examined. Table 18 shows that both variables are strongly related.

	Utility	
	r_s	p
Q40	0,693	0,001
Q41	0,621	0,001
Q42	0,461	0,002

Table 18: Correlation between the intention of use and the perceived utility.

4.8. Conclusions

The study has revealed valuable insights regarding the use of avatars in different settings, namely work, education, and leisure. The results have shown that users have a highly positive intention to use avatars in the work and education contexts. But it should also be taken into account that the users of the study come from the university field. This suggests that avatars can be a promising tool for online meetings and training sessions. Another limitation of the study is that it has only taken into account the user's experience with their own avatar. Interaction with avatars such as an interlocutor or an assistant, for example, has not been considered.

The theory that the sense of presence is crucial in avatar usage has been confirmed by the results. As the feeling of presence increases, users perceive the avatars as more useful and express a higher intention to use them. Moreover, the presence factor is inversely related to technostress caused by avatar appearance. To maximize the benefits of avatars, it is essential to focus on increasing the sense of ownership and minimizing the perception of body changes in the avatar.

One significant finding is that technostress related to avatar use is not particularly high. However, concerns about avatar appearance increase, especially among younger users who may have insecurities about their physical appearance. To mitigate this issue, it is recommended to allow users to customize their avatars while ensuring that the avatars closely resemble their real-life appearance.

Regarding privacy fears, the results show that in general, users have low privacy concerns when using avatars. However, this fear increased when users were informed that someone else could use their avatar. To address this, transparency about data usage and protection measures is crucial. Additionally, increasing the sense of ownership and reducing the perception of body changes can help alleviate privacy concerns.

Based on the importance of presence and the results related to avatar types, it is concluded that the best type of avatar to enhance presence is a realistic representation of the user with good image quality. This aligns with user preferences in work and education settings, where users prefer avatars that allow them to be presented in the best possible quality.

Finally, the study highlights the significance of users' prior experience with virtual reality. Experience in virtual reality positively correlates with increased presence, perceived usefulness, and intention to use avatars. This emphasizes the need for user-friendly manuals, excellent customer service, and comprehensive tutorials to help users adapt to the avatar system.

In conclusion, avatars offer great potential for enhancing online interactions and meetings, particularly in professional and educational settings. By focusing on increasing presence and addressing user concerns about appearance and privacy, avatars can become a valuable tool for improving virtual interactions and user experiences.

5. Requirements summary

This section will summarize the requirements extracted from the previous sections of the document.

Problem P1: To ensure an adequate usability, it is necessary to satisfy several factors. Among them should be an intuitive design, easy to learn and easy to remember.

Mitigation: Although it is difficult to achieve a system with good usability without conducting studies, some problems can be prevented by:

1. **Intuitive and Easy-to-Learn Design:** The system must be designed in a way that users can easily understand and learn its functionalities without extensive training.
2. **User Advisory Board Input:** To ensure that the system meets the needs of the target users, samples and mock-ups of different interface components should be presented to the User Advisory Board. This doesn't necessarily have to be graphical representations; any method that allows the User Advisory Board to visualize the different components of the interface can be used. Feedback from the board should be incorporated to meet user expectations.
3. **Ergonomic Design Principles:** Following ergonomic design principles is essential to create a user-friendly system that minimizes physical and cognitive strain.
4. **Usability Studies:** Conducting usability studies at various stages of the project is crucial to identify potential issues and ensure an appropriate level of usability. Regular usability testing can help in detecting and addressing any usability problems that may arise during development.

Problem P2: Technofatigue caused by the lack of non-verbal communication of an avatar and by distractions that reduce attention to the interlocutor.

Mitigation:

1. **Avatar with Body and Arms:** The avatar used in the system should have a complete body and arms, along with hand-tracking capability. This will enhance the non-verbal communication aspects and make the interactions more natural and engaging.
2. **Emotional Expressions:** The avatar should have the ability to display emotions. This feature will enable users to express themselves more

effectively and perceive emotions from their interlocutors, reducing techno-fatigue caused by the lack of non-verbal cues.

3. **Minimize Distractions:** The system should be designed to minimize distractions during conversations. This can be achieved by reducing the number of elements that may divert the users' attention away from their interlocutors.

Problem P3: Cybersickness.

Mitigation:

1. **Static Backgrounds with Proper Lighting:** The system should use static backgrounds with appropriate lighting to avoid excessive motion that can lead to cybersickness. This will allow users to focus on their interlocutors or objects without increasing factors that cause discomfort.
2. **Balance between Presence and Cybersickness:** Striking a balance between creating a strong sense of presence and minimizing factors that contribute to cybersickness is crucial. Further studies should be conducted in the later stages of the project to optimize this balance.
3. **Include Break Recommendations:** The system should incorporate recommendations for users to take breaks after a certain period of use. Regular breaks can help prevent and alleviate cybersickness symptoms, ensuring a more comfortable and enjoyable experience.

Problem P4: Technostress for fear of new technologies.

Mitigation: Ensure that the user is able to learn how to use the platform in a simple way and understands the benefits of using it. This can be approached in different ways:

1. **User-Friendly Manual:** Develop a user-friendly and easily accessible manual that provides quick access to essential information about the platform. The manual should be easy to use and understand, helping users navigate through the system effortlessly.
2. **Interactive Tutorial:** Implement an interactive tutorial within the platform to guide users through their initial steps. The tutorial should be easily accessible and provide clear instructions on how to use the platform effectively.
3. **Highlight Platform Benefits:** Ensure that users are aware of the benefits of using the platform and its various features without requiring in-depth exploration. This can be achieved through clear communication and highlighting key advantages during the onboarding process.

Problem P5: Technostress for fear of privacy.

Mitigation:

1. Clear Transparency: Provide clear and transparent information to users about how their data is collected, used, and protected within the platform.
2. Data Security Measures: Implement robust data security measures to safeguard user information from unauthorized access or breaches.
3. User Consent and Control: Offer users control over their data by allowing them to provide explicit consent for data collection and offering options to opt-out or delete their data if desired.

Problem P6: Technostress problems with the avatar.

Mitigation:

1. Enhance User Presence: Increase the feeling of presence for users within the system. This can be achieved by using avatars that closely resemble the users and prioritize realism and high-quality visuals.
2. Avatar Customization: Offer users the option to customize their avatars according to their preferences. Allowing users to personalize their avatars can reduce technostress related to the appearance of the avatar (clothes, accessories, etc.).
3. Realistic Avatar Representation: While offering customization options, ensure that the avatars created are as close as possible to the user's physical appearance. Striving for realistic representation can enhance user comfort and reduce any discomfort associated with non-realistic avatars.

ANNEX A: References

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ANNEX B: Study protocol

Summary of documents in the protocol:

1. Consent form and Confidentiality note
2. Study procedure ready to print.
3. Questionnaire PRE-Study.
4. Questionnaire Study Part 1.
5. Questionnaire Study Part 2.
6. Questionnaire Study Part 3.
7. Questionnaire Study Part 4.
8. Questionnaire POST-Study.

CONSENT FORM and CONFIDENTIALITY NOTE

[Place, Date]

We are inviting you to participate in a research project conducted by [organization name]. This letter provides you with information. Please, take your time to read it and discuss it with others before you decide on your participation. Do not hesitate to ask questions (see contact below).

Title of the Project: “CORTEX²”

Who are we?

The project CORTEX² is a European research project. It is carried out by different partners in Europe. [NAME ORGANISATION] is responsible for carrying out the project in [NAME COUNTRY].

What is our study about?

Video conferencing and mixed reality are both forms of communication but based on very different technologies. Video conferencing does not provide an in-person feel to meetings and has several other drawbacks. In contrast, mixed reality has emerged as a technology that can provide a genuine feeling of presence, and better collaboration tools. The EU-funded CORTEX² project will bridge the divide between widespread video conferencing tools and innovative XR-based solutions to democratize the adoption of next-generation eXtended Reality tele-cooperation by industrial sectors and SMEs.

CORTEX²'s mission is to bridge the gap between widespread videoconferencing tools and state-of-the-art XR-based solutions, democratizing the adoption of next-generation extended reality telecooperation among a large number of industrial segments and SMEs. To do this, our project will provide: central system with open APIs and the organization of open calls for extensions to more technical modules and more use cases in various segments.

In order for users to use this system, one tool that they will need is the use of a virtual identity to represent them in it. In other words, an avatar. But there are different types of avatars that the user can choose from, so in this study it is intended:

- To obtain and evaluate the user's opinion on the use of avatars.
- To obtain and evaluate the user's preferences in the use of avatars.

To do this, three types of avatars will be used in this study:

- **Hyperrealistic:** A digitally created representation of a human being with an exceptionally high level of detail and realism.

- **Not realistic:** A digital representation of a human being intentionally deviating from realistic appearance and features, adopting stylized or abstract styles.
- **Another person:** A digital representation of another person who is not the user.

What do we expect from you during this study?

We invite you to participate in a session that will span approximately 20 to 30 minutes. During this session, you will have the opportunity to utilize a system that transforms a photograph into a lifelike avatar. The designated research personnel will supply you with all the required materials and provide training on how to operate this system. Please note that the focus of evaluation will be on the avatars presented, rather than the performance of the PC used.

Before starting the study, you will answer a preliminary questionnaire where you will be asked questions about your experience with various technologies. After using each type of avatar, you will answer a questionnaire for you to evaluate the avatar and how you have felt using it. And at the end you will answer a last questionnaire where you can compare each of the avatars.

During the session, the person in charge will answer any questions that may arise.

What happens with your data?

The data that is gathered from the interviews and from your use with the system is completely anonym. It cannot be linked to your own identity. The anonymized data will be stored for the duration of the project (December 2025) and then completely destroyed. You can access this data by asking your contact person.

Are there any risks to taking part?

There are no risks or known contraindications associated with using the system and activities or completing the questionnaires.

Are there any potential benefits to taking part?

Your cooperation will help us to better understand the user preferences. As this project is still in the research phase, we cannot be sure that you will benefit from taking part.

Do I have to take part? Can I stop taking part if I want to? Your participation is completely voluntary. You can stop taking part and withdraw at any time during the project. You do not have to explain why you do not want to take part, nor would you have to explain why you want to stop taking part.

If you agree to participate in the study, please sign the informed consent to indicate that you participate voluntary and that you have received all you require.

Will I get paid for taking part? You will not be paid for taking part.

***Contact details support staff:**

Name of the contact person: _____

Company/Organization name: _____

Address: _____

Email: _____

Phone number: _____

*** Contact details**

Name of the researcher: _____

Company/Organization name: _____

Address: _____

Email: _____

Phone number: _____

Study protocol ready to print

Inclusion criteria:

- People with experience in video conferencing (e.g., researchers).
- People with VR experience.
- Age range: 18 to 65 years, with minimal ICT knowledge.
- Trying to achieve gender parity.

Summary of the Procedure

The test should be conducted individually.

- PRE-STUDY: Explanation and consent signing, pre-test assessment of prior knowledge, and collection of sociodemographic data.
- Test 1: Personal hyper-realistic Avatar - Questionnaire 1.
- Test 2: Personal non-realistic Avatar - Questionnaire 2.
- Test 3: Other person Avatar - Questionnaire 3.
- Test 4: Exchange of hyper-realistic avatars with the researcher using the participant's avatar - Questionnaire 4.
- POST-STUDY: Final questionnaire.

Detailed procedure

The following procedure will be followed for each test:

- **Introduction:** The video avatar will appear on the screen with the user in front of their PC. The screen will solely display the avatar without any additional visuals. The user will be instructed to keep their gaze fixed on the screen throughout the entire experiment.

** In Test 4, the initial video avatar will either be controlled by researcher. The user will observe as their own avatar is manipulated by the other person.*

- **Avatar Description:** The user will be provided with an explanation of the type of avatar being used:
 - **Hyper-realistic:** A digitally created representation of a human being with an exceptionally high level of detail and realism.

- **Not realistic:** A digital representation of a human being intentionally deviating from realistic appearance and features, adopting stylized or abstract styles.
- **Another person:** A Hiper-realistic digital representation of another person who is not the user.
- **Familiarization:** The user will become acquainted with the avatar by performing head movements and gestures. Duration: 15 - 30 seconds.
- **Interview:** The researcher will simulate an interview with the user, asking personal questions. The user is not obligated to answer, and if uncomfortable, they may request a question change. The objective is to encourage the user to engage in conversation, divert attention from the avatar, and observe its movements during responses. Duration: 1-2 minutes.
- **Questionnaire:** While the researcher prepares for the next experiment, the user will complete the corresponding questionnaire.

Sample "Interview" Questions

- Good morning, my name is X. What is your name?
- Where are you from?
- Where do you work? Could you describe your job?
- Can you tell me a bit about yourself? What are your interests and hobbies?
- Where did you study?
- What kind of work or study environment do you prefer?
- How do you interact with others? Do you prefer working in a team or individually? Why?
- What are your expectations for the future? Where do you see yourself in five years?
- Tell me a bit about your upbringing.
- Do you have any experience with VR? Could you share your first encounter with a virtual reality headset?
- Do you have any pets? Please describe them.
- Tell me about your family.

QUESTIONNAIRE PRE-STUDY

User code: Center:

AGE:

Sex:

Man	Woman

What is your level of education?

Primary	Secondary	University degree	Master	Doctorate

Q1. How many times have you held a video conference related to your work?

Never	1time	1 to 10 times	More than 10 times	Frequently

Q2. How many times have you held a video conference that is related to education (Giving or receiving classes)?

Never	1time	1 to 10 times	More than 10 times	Frequently

Q3. How many times have you held a video conference that is not related to your job or education?

Never	1time	1 to 10 times	More than 10 times	Frequently

Q4. How many times have you used a reality virtual system before today?

Never	1time	1 to 10 times	More than 10 times	Frequently

Q5. How many times have you used a virtual reality system at work (for example a meeting)?

Never	1time	1 to 10 times	More than 10 times	Frequently

Q6. How many times have you used a virtual reality system in education?

Never	1time	1 to 10 times	More than 10 times	Frequently

Q7. How many times have you used a virtual reality system in leisure (games, meetings, social events...)?

Never	1time	1 to 10 times	More than 10 times	Frequently

Q8. Do you have any virtual reality devices at home?

No	Yes

QUESTIONNAIRE STUDY PART 1

Avatar Type: _____

User code: _____

Mark with an X your level of agreement of the following statements.

Strongly disagree Somewhat disagree Neither disagree, nor agree Somewhat agree Strongly agree

Q9. It felt like the virtual face was my face

Q10. The virtual face felt like a human face.

Q11. I had the feeling that the virtual face belonged to me.

Q12. The movements of the virtual face seemed to be my own movements.

Q13. I enjoyed controlling the virtual face.

Q14. I have felt comfortable using the virtual face.

Q15. I felt as if I was controlling the movement of the virtual face.

Q16. The movements of the virtual face were synchronous with my own movements.

--	--	--	--	--

Q17. I had the illusion of owning a different face from my own.

--	--	--	--	--

Q18. I felt the need to check if my face really still looked like what I had in mind.

--	--	--	--	--

Q19. I felt as if the form or appearance of my face had changed.

--	--	--	--	--

Q20. I feel that the use of this type of avatar is an intrusion into my privacy.

--	--	--	--	--

Q21. I feel that this kind of avatar reveals private personal information without my consent.

--	--	--	--	--

QUESTIONNAIRE STUDY PART 2

Avatar Type: _____

User code: _____

Mark with an X your level of agreement of the following statements.

Strongly disagree Somewhat disagree Neither disagree, nor agree Somewhat agree Strongly agree

Q9. It felt like the virtual face was my face

Q10. The virtual face felt like a human face.

Q11. I had the feeling that the virtual face belonged to me.

Q12. The movements of the virtual face seemed to be my own movements.

Q13. I enjoyed controlling the virtual face.

Q14. I have felt comfortable using the virtual face.

Q15. I felt as if I was controlling the movement of the virtual face.

Q16. The movements of the virtual face were synchronous with my own movements.

--	--	--	--	--

Q17. I had the illusion of owning a different face from my own.

--	--	--	--	--

Q18. I felt the need to check if my face really still looked like what I had in mind.

--	--	--	--	--

Q19. I felt as if the form or appearance of my face had changed.

--	--	--	--	--

Q20. I feel that the use of this type of avatar is an intrusion into my privacy.

--	--	--	--	--

Q21. I feel that this kind of avatar reveals private personal information without my consent.

--	--	--	--	--

QUESTIONNAIRE STUDY PART 3

Avatar Type: _____

User code: _____

Mark with an X your level of agreement of the following statements.

Strongly disagree Somewhat disagree Neither disagree, nor agree Somewhat agree Strongly agree

Q9. It felt like the virtual face was my face

--	--	--	--	--

Q10. The virtual face felt like a human face.

--	--	--	--	--

Q11. I had the feeling that the virtual face belonged to me.

--	--	--	--	--

Q12. The movements of the virtual face seemed to be my own movements.

--	--	--	--	--

Q13. I enjoyed controlling the virtual face.

--	--	--	--	--

Q14. I have felt comfortable using the virtual face.

--	--	--	--	--

Q15. I felt as if I was controlling the movement of the virtual face.

--	--	--	--	--

Q16. The movements of the virtual face were synchronous with my own movements.

--	--	--	--	--

Q17. I had the illusion of owning a different face from my own.

--	--	--	--	--

Q18. I felt the need to check if my face really still looked like what I had in mind.

--	--	--	--	--

Q19. I felt as if the form or appearance of my face had changed.

--	--	--	--	--

Q20. I feel that the use of this type of avatar is an intrusion into my privacy.

--	--	--	--	--

Q21. I feel that this kind of avatar reveals private personal information without my consent.

--	--	--	--	--

QUESTIONNAIRE STUDY PART 4

Avatar Type: _____

User code: _____

Mark with an X your level of agreement of the following statements.

Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither disagree, nor agree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
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Q9. It felt like the virtual face was my face

--	--	--	--	--

Q10. The virtual face felt like a human face.

--	--	--	--	--

Q11. I had the feeling that the virtual face belonged to me.

--	--	--	--	--

Q12. The movements of the virtual face seemed to be my own movements.

--	--	--	--	--

Q13. I enjoyed controlling the virtual face.

--	--	--	--	--

Q14. I have felt comfortable using the virtual face.

--	--	--	--	--

Q15. I felt as if I was controlling the movement of the virtual face.

--	--	--	--	--

Q16. The movements of the virtual face were synchronous with my own movements.

--	--	--	--	--

Q17. I had the illusion of owning a different face from my own.

--	--	--	--	--

Q18. I felt the need to check if my face really still looked like what I had in mind.

--	--	--	--	--

Q19. I felt as if the form or appearance of my face had changed.

--	--	--	--	--

Q20. I feel that the use of this type of avatar is an intrusion into my privacy.

--	--	--	--	--

Q21. I feel that this kind of avatar reveals private personal information without my consent.

--	--	--	--	--

QUESTIONNAIRE POST-STUDY

User code: _____

Mark with an X your level of agreement of the following questions.

Less agree

More Agree

Q22. Do you feel or would you feel pressured or stressed about maintaining a "perfect" image or appearance through your avatar?

--	--	--	--	--

Q23. Do you feel or think you would feel anxiety or stress when comparing your avatar to other people's avatars in virtual environments?

--	--	--	--	--

Q24. Do you experience or think that you would experience difficulties in expressing your true identity or personality through your avatar?

--	--	--	--	--

Q25. Do you or would you feel uncomfortable or stressed about the lack of privacy or the potential exposure of your real identity while using an avatar?

--	--	--	--	--

Q26. Do you feel or think you would feel that using avatars in virtual environments exhausts you emotionally or mentally?

--	--	--	--	--

Q27. Do you experience or think you would experience worries or stress related to the possibility of your avatar being judged or discriminated against by other users?

--	--	--	--	--

Q28. Do you feel or think that you would feel that the use of avatars in virtual environments negatively affects your self-esteem or self-confidence?

--	--	--	--	--

Mark with an x the type of avatar you would prefer in each case. You can select more than one.

	Hyper-Realistic	Realistic	Non-realistic	Other person
Q29. Working meeting with your team.				
Q30. Working meeting with clients or partners.				
Q31. Working meeting with senior positions (managers, project managers...).				
Q32. Education: Attending a class.				
Q33. Education: Teaching a class.				
Q34. Leisure: Games where you interact with other players.				
Q35. Leisure: Meeting with friends.				
Q36. Leisure: Social event (for example a talk).				

Mark with an X your level of agreement of the following statements.

Strongly disagree Somewhat disagree Neither disagree, nor agree Somewhat agree Strongly agree

Q37. I find it useful to use an avatar in a work meeting.

--	--	--	--	--

Q38. I find it useful to use an avatar in education.

--	--	--	--	--

Q39. I consider it useful to use an avatar in leisure applications.

--	--	--	--	--

Q40. In the future I would be willing to use an avatar in a work meeting.

--	--	--	--	--

Q41. In the future I would be willing to use an avatar in education.

--	--	--	--	--

Q42. In the future I would be willing to use an avatar in leisure applications.

--	--	--	--	--